

**TALABALARDA NIZOLI XULQNI BARTARAF ETISHDA TRENING
DASTURLARINING AHAMIYATI**

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Annotatsiya. maqolada treninglarning nazariy asoslari, talabalardagi nizoli xulqni bartaraf etishda treninglarning o‘rni va ahamiyati, treninglarni tashkil etish bosqichlari, asosiy yo‘nalishlari haqida yoritilgan. Shuningdek, trening dasturining asosiy tamoyillari, mashg‘ulotda talabalardagi emotsiyalar, trening natijasida kuzatiladigan o‘zgarishlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: trening, nizoli xulq, dastur, bosqich, yo‘nalish, tamoyil, hissiy beqarorlik, psixologik moslashuv, emotsiyalar, muloqot, nizoli holat, “hamkorlik”, “murosa”, strategiyalar.

**THE IMPORTANCE OF TRAINING PROGRAMS IN ELIMINATING CONFLICT
BEHAVIOR IN STUDENTS**

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Annotation. the article discusses the theoretical foundations of training, the role and importance of training in eliminating conflict behavior in students, the stages and main directions of organizing training. It also describes the main principles of the training program, emotions in students during the training, and changes observed as a result of the training.

Keywords: training, conflict behavior, program, stage, direction, principle, emotional instability, psychological adaptation, emotions, communication, conflict situation, "cooperation", "compromise", strategies.

**ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ТРЕНИНГОВЫХ ПРОГРАММ В УСТРАНЕНИИ КОНФЛИКТНОГО
ПОВЕДЕНИЯ СТУДЕНТОВ**

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Аннотация. в статье рассматриваются теоретические основы тренинга, роль и значение тренинга в устранении конфликтного поведения студентов, этапы и основные направления организации тренинга. Описываются основные принципы тренинговой программы, эмоции студентов во время тренинга и изменения, наблюдаемые в результате тренинга.

Ключевые слова: тренинг, конфликтное поведение, программа, этап, направление, принцип, эмоциональная нестабильность, психологическая адаптация, эмоции, общение, конфликтная ситуация, «сотрудничество», «компромисс», стратегии.

Introduction. In today's era of globalization and the rapid development of the digital society, the socio-psychological adaptation, interpersonal communication and emotional stability of students are considered one of the urgent problems. As a result of the increased flow of information, increased workload, and the growing competitive environment in social networks, many students are faced with emotional instability, fatigue, and a tendency to conflict situations. In such conditions, eliminating conflict behavior in students, forming constructive communication skills, and developing social behavior based on patience, empathy, and cultural compromise are among the important

psychological tasks facing today's education system. The psychological training program developed in this direction is aimed at forming a conscious approach of students to conflict situations, managing their emotions, and developing a culture of cooperation and peace.

Literature review on the topic. The training program is based on strengthening students' socio-emotional competencies, and its scientific and methodological basis is based on the theoretical developments of such scientists as I.M. Sechenov, L.S. Vygotsky, K. Thomas, R. Kilmann, A.A. Bodalev, and D. Amirkhan on social relations, stress management, and conflict resolution. According to the classification of conflict resolution methods by K. Thomas and R. Kilmann, a person uses five different strategies in conflict situations: competition, compromise, withdrawal, adaptation, and cooperation. Based on this approach, the main goal of the training program is to teach students the strategies of "cooperation" and "compromise", and to form a culture of non-aggressive communication.

Research methodology.

The training was organized on the basis of the following main stages:

1. Diagnostic preparation stage. At this stage, students' attitude to conflict situations, level of emotional stability, behavioral culture and level of communication competence are determined. Through questionnaires, psychological interviews and observations, it is studied how students enter into conflicts and choose ways out of them. At this stage, students are prepared to understand the sources of stress, aggression or uncertainty in themselves and channel them positively.
2. Training sessions stage. This stage is the main content part of the training program. The program consists of 12 thematic sessions, each of which is aimed at developing a specific psychological mechanism. Sessions such as "Understanding the essence of the conflict", "My feelings", "The difference between me and others", "Behaving in a dispute", "Expressing your opinion peacefully", "Empathy is the key to mutual understanding", "Finding solutions in cooperation", "Stress management", "Culture of calm communication" are conducted based on interactive methods. The sessions use role-playing games, situational discussions, dramatic scenes, elements of art therapy, musical relaxation, mutual exchange of ideas and reflective writing.
3. The stage of understanding personal changes. Students analyze their own actions and feelings and come to understand the changes. Based on the "I-you" model, they develop the skills of listening to the opinions of others, expressing their position, and self-control. At this stage, students acquire values such as "not being afraid to speak their mind", "maintaining respect in conflict", "patience in communication".
4. Evaluation and Reinforcement Phase. At the end of the program, students will have the opportunity to evaluate their progress and reinforce the knowledge and skills they have acquired during the training. Through group discussions, reflective essay writing, and self-analysis exercises, they will understand their development.

The training program is based on the following psychological principles:

- The principle of activity and participation - students actively participate in each session, relying on their own life experiences.
- The principle of reflexivity - a person analyzes their behavior and consciously approaches changes.
- The principle of empathic approach - understanding the feelings of others, mitigating conflicts by taking their point of view into account.

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- The principle of systematization - ensuring the interconnection of emotional, social and communicative components.
- The principle of humanism - respecting the personal opinions, experiences and feelings of each participant.

Analysis and results (Analysis and results).

During the training sessions, students learn to manage their emotions, express their position in a culturally appropriate manner in communication, and make the right decisions in stressful situations. They begin to choose a “cooperation” strategy instead of “attack” or “withdrawal” in conflict situations. During group activities, students strengthen mutual trust, develop the skills of listening to each other, and respectfully express their opinions.

As a dynamic of personal development, students develop patience, a tendency to compromise, self-awareness, and the ability to communicate with others based on mutual respect. At the end of the training, they learn to control their emotions, seek positive solutions instead of negative reactions in conflict situations, and combine personal opinions with the interests of the team.

During the training, observations were conducted by teachers and psychologists, which revealed that the students' level of communication culture, mutual respect, and peace culture increased. Participants will apply the skills they learned in their life experiences and prioritize a compromise approach in teamwork.

Training program for eliminating conflict behavior in students

Session №	Session topic	Session objective	Methods	Duration
1	Introduction to training. Building mutual trust	Creating a positive psychological atmosphere in the group, introducing participants	Introduction game, "What does my name mean?" technique	45 minute
2	What is a conflict?	Explain the nature of conflict situations and distinguish their main types	"Brainstorming", situational analysis	60 minute
3	Me and my feelings	Developing the ability to understand, recognize, and express emotional states	"Emotion cards", mimicry game	60 minute
4	Sources of conflict	Analysis of psychological factors that cause conflict	Case study, “Cause and effect chain” chart	60 minute
5	Conflict management styles	Teaching how to choose constructive actions in a conflict situation	Role-playing, “Stop and Think!” technique	45 minute

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6	Expressing one's opinion in a civilized manner.	Developing the skill of expressing one's opinion peacefully in the process of communication.	"I-message" technique, conversation analysis.	60 minute
7	Aggression management	Controlling emotional outbursts in conflict situations and directing them into a positive channel	Reflective training, "Inner Voice" technique	45 minute
8	Empathy and listening culture	Developing the skills of understanding, feeling and active listening to others	"If I were him...", dialogue game	60 minute
9	Finding solutions in cooperation	Strengthening the skills of resolving conflict situations based on positive communication	Group discussion, "Circle of Agreement" exercise	60 minute
10	Self-management	Teaching mechanisms for maintaining calm and self-control in stressful situations	Breathing exercises, visualization techniques	60 minute
11	Muloqotdagi to'siqlar Barriers to Communication	Identifying and correcting communication errors that cause conflict	Exercise "Wall in Communication", situation analysis	45 minute
12	The art of compromise	Reconciling opposing views and building a culture of compromise	The game "Two-way win", the debate method	60 minute
13	Culture of Peace	Nonviolent conflict resolution and instilling the value of peace	"Tree of Peace" technique, positive exchange of ideas	45 minute
14	Work in a team	Increasing cooperation, mutual assistance, and responsibility	Teamwork, "Towards a Goal" game	60 minute

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15	Ways to reduce stress	Learning stress-reducing techniques in conflict situations	Music therapy, elements of art therapy	60 minute
16	Defending my opinion	Developing the ability to express one's position in a non-pressured manner	"My opinion" technique, role-playing	60 minute
17	Mediation in disputes	Learn to mediate conflicts and maintain a neutral position	"Third Party" exercise, mediator role	60 minute
18	Developing calmness and patience	Maintaining patience and calm in difficult situations	Dhikr exercises, visualization of "Inner Peace"	45 minute
19	Positive communication and feedback	Generating positive feedback, developing sincere communication	"Positive Words Circle", "Listening Without Judging" Exercise	60 minute
20	Training wrap-up and reflection	Understanding change, sharing experiences, and analyzing personal development	"How have I changed?", group discussion	60 minute

Conclusions.

The following qualitative changes are observed as a result of the training: students become aware of their own emotions, develop an empathetic attitude towards others, learn to maintain social balance, strive for peace and cooperation in the process of communication. They begin to perceive conflict not as a confrontation, but as an opportunity for personal and social growth.

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